

Embryonic and Larval Development of Ornamental Fish Japanese Koi (*Cyprinus Rubrofusca*) by Induced Breeding Technique

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Abstract:

The present study was undertaken to investigate induced breeding, embryonic development, and larval growth of Japanese koi (*Cyprinus rubrofusca*) under captive conditions with the objective of enhancing ornamental fish production. The experiment was carried out at Sams Discus India (Ornamental Fish Hatchery), Pen, Raigad, Maharashtra, India. Mature and healthy brooders were selected and injected with Ovaprim hormone according to dosage. The fertilization rate was recorded as 91%. Eggs hatched within 45–48 hours at water temperature of 26–28°C. The survival rate was enhanced up to 87% when larvae were fed live food organisms (*Daphnia* and *Moina*), along with artificial pellet feed. The results shows that induced breeding using Ovaprim is highly effective. The short embryonic period, high fecundity, and larval survival rate suggest that Japanese koi can be successfully bred even under varying climatic conditions.

Keywords: *Ovaprim, Fecundity, Survival.*

Introduction:

The ornamental fisheries sector is one of the fastest-growing sectors of aquaculture due to its high economic value, export potential, and increasing global demand. India possesses vast freshwater resources, with nearly 90% of ornamental fish species being freshwater origin, of which approximately 98% are cultured and only 2% are captured from the wild resources. The remaining 10% comprise marine ornamental fishes, largely wild-caught. Koi carps generally live up to 15-24 years. Being hardy, it is highly suitable for garden pools and aquarium keeping ([Hussian et al., 2014](#)).

Japanese koi (*Cyprinus rubrofusca*), also known as Nishikigoi, is one of the most popular ornamental fish species worldwide due to its vibrant coloration, aesthetic appeal, and adaptability to captive conditions. Koi are widely

cultured for aquarium trade, garden ponds, and landscaping purposes. However, consistent seed availability remains a major challenge for the ornamental fish industry. Induced breeding techniques play a crucial role in reproductive constraints and ensuring year-round seed production of Koi fish. Even though many ornamental fish have been induced to spawn in captivity, the larvae of only a few species have been successfully reared in captivity ([Holt, 2003](#); [Olivotto et al., 2003](#)). Understanding embryonic and larval development is essential for improving hatchery management, increasing survival rates, and optimizing feeding strategies. The present study aims to study the induced breeding techniques, embryonic stages, and larval development of Japanese koi under controlled hatchery conditions.

Materials and Methods:

1. Experimental Site:

The experiment was conducted at Sams Discus India (Ornamental Fish Hatchery), Pen, Raigad District, Maharashtra, India, during March–April 2023. This is well designed breeding hatchery of ornamental fishes consisting all components.

2. Selection of Brooders:

Mature and healthy Japanese koi brooders were selected based on sexual dimorphism. Females were identified by a bulging abdomen and soft belly, while males exhibited slender bodies and rough pectoral fins. Average body weight of females ranged from 0.8–1.2 kg, while males ranged from 0.6–1.0 kg. Brooders (Males and Females) were fed with high protein feed for 25 days to increase quality of milt and eggs respectively.

Table No. 1: Sexual dimorphism in koi fish

Character	Male	Female
Belly Size	Slender	Bulgy
Pectoral Fin	Rough	Smooth
Secondary sexual characteristics	Pink coloured vent Tubercles appear on the face Oozes milt	Vent will be rounder and pinker than male Tubercles absent Oozes eggs
Size	Smaller	Larger

3. Induced Breeding Technique:

Induced breeding was carried out using Ovaprim hormone. Males were injected with 0.2 ml/kg body weight and females with 0.3–0.4 ml/kg body weight. The injections were administered at the base of pectoral fin.

4. Breeding Setup:

Injected brooders were released into breeding tanks containing clean, aerated water. Plastic bags, PVC pipes, and nylon ropes were used as spawning substrates and hiding places. The breeding ratio was maintained at 1:1 (male: female). Spawning activity was observed after 4–5 hours post-injection.

5. Egg Collection and Incubation:

Eggs were adhesive and immediately stick on substrate. Eggs were incubated in well-aerated water under controlled conditions. Water quality parameters were maintained as follows: temperature 26–28°C, pH 7.2–7.4, and dissolved oxygen above 6 mg/L. The incubation period of eggs depends largely on water quality parameters such as salinity and temperature (Kuo et al., 1973; Liao, 1975).

6. Observation of Embryonic and Larval Development:

Embryonic and larval development was observed at regular intervals using a light microscope. Photographs and videos were taken to record various developmental stages. Larvae were monitored until 20 days post-hatching. In the present study the developmental stages of koi carp were divided into six stages. viz., embryo, hatchling, larva, post-larva, fry and fingerling (Jhingran and Pullin, 1985)

7. Feeding and Survival Assessment:

Larvae were initially fed live food organisms such as *Daphnia* and *Moina*. After the early larval stage, finely powdered artificial pellet feed was introduced. Survival rate was calculated based on the number of larvae surviving at the end of the observation period. Live feed helps to increase survival rate along with artificial food.

Fig. 1 A: Live feed daphnia, B: Microscopic view of daphnia

Fig. 2 A: Selected matured brooders, B: Conditioning of brooders, C: Male chasing females, D: Courtship behavior, E: Adhesive Eggs on Polyethene bag, F: Adhesive Eggs on PVC Pipe, G: Fertilized Egg, H: Twenty hours old embryo, I: Thirty-six hours embryo, J: Hatched Larva, K: One day old larva, L: Four Days old larva

Results and Discussion:

1. Induced Breeding Performance:

Spawning commenced within 4–5 hours after hormone injection, indicating a positive response to Ovaprim. The fertilization rate was recorded as 91%, demonstrating high breeding efficiency. Similar results have been reported in earlier studies on koi breeding (Freeman, 1987). No any mortality or injury seen in brooders.

2. Embryonic Development:

Embryonic development was rapid and well-defined. Cleavage stages were observed soon after fertilization, followed by blastula and gastrula stages. Organogenesis occurred within a

short period, and embryos hatched within 45–48 hours post-fertilization. The short embryonic duration may be attributed to optimal water temperature and proper aeration.

3. Larval Development:

Newly hatched larvae were transparent with a prominent yolk sac. Yolk sac absorption was completed within 72 hours. Pigmentation began appearing on the body within 5–6 days, and fin rays developed gradually. By 15–20 days, larvae exhibited distinct coloration patterns and active swimming behavior. After 3 days, the larvae started exogenous feeding. ([Jameson and Santhanam \(1996\)](#))

Table 1. Larval development of Japanese koi

Larval Age (days)	Length (mm)	Characteristics
0	Just hatched	Transparent body with heavy yolk sac
1	2.7–2.9	Fin fold originates; large yolk sac
3	5.0–5.4	Yolk sac absorbed; eye pigmentation
6	5.8–6.0	Yellow pigments and silver band visible
15	6.8–7.0	Fin rays differentiated; darker pigments
20	12–14	Pigmentation varied; color patterns visible

4. Survival Rate and Feeding:

Survival rate increased up to 87% when larvae were fed live food organisms such as *Daphnia* and *Moina*. Live feed played a crucial

role in early larval nutrition and help reduce mortality. Similar observations were made by Kuo et al. (1973), emphasizing the importance of live feed in larval stages.

Fig 3: Key Points for Koi Breeding

Conclusion:

The present study concludes that induced breeding of Japanese koi using Ovaprim hormone is highly effective under captive conditions. High fertilization and hatching rates, short embryonic development, and rapid larval growth make Japanese koi suitable for commercial ornamental fish culture. The use of live feed significantly enhances larval survival. The findings provide a strong scientific basis for large-scale seed production and sustainable development of the ornamental fisheries sector.

References:

1. Balon, E. K. (1985) The theory of saltatory ontogeny and life history model revisited. In: Balon, E. K. (ed.), Early life history of fishes developments in EBF 5. ISBN90-6193-514-8. W. Junk Publ. Dordrecht, Netherlands. pp.13-28.
2. Balon, E. K. (1999) Alternative ways how to become a definitive phenotype or a juvenile (and on some persisting linguistic offences). *Environ. Biol. Fish.* 56: 17-38.
3. Boglinoe, C., B. Bertolini., M. Russiello, S. Cataudella. (1992). Embryonic and larval development of the thick-lipped mullet (*Chelon labrosus*) under controlled reproduction conditions. *Aquaculture* 101: 349-359.
4. Carlos, A. M., M. C. Sanchez, G. S. Papp, A. D. Parra and L. G. Ross. (2002) Observations on spawning, early development and growth of the puffer fish *Sphoeroides annulatus*. *J. Aqua. Trop* 17: 59-66.
5. Freeman, E. (1987). Breeding koi: Sexing, spawning, incubation of koi eggs, development of koi eggs and fry. *Aquaculture*, 35, 41–53.
6. Holt, G.J., (2003). Research on culturing the early life stages of marine ornamental fish. *Mar. Ornament.Spp. Collect. Cult. Conserv.*, 251-254.
7. Hussain, T., Verma, A.K., Tiwari, V.K., Prakash, C., Rathore, G., Shete, A.P. and Nuwansi, K.K.T., (2014). Optimizing koi carp, *Cyprinus carpio var. koi* (Linnaeus, 1758), stocking density and nutrient recycling with spinach in an aquaponic system. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.*, 45: 652-661. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jwas.12159>
8. Jameson, J.D. and Santhanam, R., (1996). *Manual of ornamental fishes and farming technologies*. Tamil Nadu Veterinary and Animal Sciences University, Chennai, pp.50-60.
9. Jhingran, V. G. and R. S.V. Pullin. 1985) A Hatchery manual for common, chinese and Indian Major carps. Asian Development Bank. International Centre for Living Aquatic Resources Management. Manila, The Philippines. P.191.
10. Kuo, C. M., Shehadeh, Z. H., & Milison, M. (1973). A preliminary report on the development, growth, and survival of laboratory-reared larvae of the grey mullet, *Mugil cephalus* (L.). *Journal of Fish Biology*, 5, 459–470.
11. Liao, I. C. (1975). Effects of environmental factors on fish embryonic development. *Aquaculture Research*, 6, 21–28.
12. Liao, I.-C. (1975) Experiments on the induced breeding of the grey mullet in Taiwan from 1963-1973. *Aquaculture* 6: 31-58. Meehan, W. E. 2002. Fish culture in ponds and other inland waters. 1st ed. H. R. publishing house, Pilani, India. p. 285.